

ADAPTIVE AIDING: CRAWLING BEFORE WE WALK

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ABSTRACT

Implementation of full-up adaptive aiding systems is difficult and expensive, requiring the programming of many variables. Two techniques are proposed for simplifying adaptive aid development by severely limiting the levels and kinds of assistance provided. These simplifying strategies are termed *operator tailoring* and *mission-phase tailoring*. Each of the techniques has been used at the Naval Weapons Center to design a different military system, both of which might be termed "semi-adaptive aiding" computer programs. The two strategies rely on partitioning the levels and kinds of aiding into a few discrete states, rather than providing a continuum of assistance for all possible conditions. Development approach, advantages, disadvantages, and status of these two techniques and the resulting systems are discussed.

BACKGROUND

Concepts of Aiding

In a relatively static environment, simple decision aids and the automation of difficult tasks have been popular ways to help system operators use difficult or intricate systems properly. However, in dynamic situations, the level of aiding and the ways in which the aiding system and the human interact should change as task demands vary [1]. Operator aids that adapt the help they provide to fit current conditions and operator needs are called "adaptive aids".

Complex conventional and artificial intelligence computer systems have been proposed as adaptive aids [2, 3, 4]. For each mission phase or major task, such dynamic aiding programs would "know" what tasks must be performed and would "know" the current task criticality levels. In addition, they would

be able to sense or calculate the operator's physical and mental states and the present workload level.

Based on the required tasks and the operator's condition, an adaptive aiding system continuously would evaluate whether the operator is capable of satisfactorily carrying out the required tasks. If he or she is not, the system then would initiate a change in the level and kind of aid provided. That is, the aiding system would (a) define precisely what must be done, (b) prioritize the remaining tasks, and (c) rapidly carry out the important ones--while perhaps keeping the operator informed of what is happening.

Problems with Adaptive Aiding

Implementation of dynamic aiding systems has proven difficult and expensive, especially since such computer-based systems must self-adapt and must provide answers and assistance in real time [5, 6]. Development problems have been due partly to attempts to include large numbers of variables in the aiding system in order to provide continuous aiding assistance for almost any situation that might arise throughout a mission.

A SIMPLIFIED APPROACH TO ADAPTIVE AIDING

Two different dynamic aiding development strategies or techniques have been used by the Human Factors Branch at the Naval Weapons Center (NWC) to minimize the quantity of required system variables and to enable real-time software operation. These strategies have been termed *operator tailoring* and *mission-phase tailoring* of aiding levels (Figure 1). Both techniques rely on partitioning the levels and kinds of aid into a few

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assistance levels covering all possible conditions. The result has been the prototyping of what might be termed "semi-adaptive" aiding systems.

Figure 1. Simplifying Strategies for Development of Adaptive Aids, and NWC's Resulting Operator Aiding Systems

The two strategies are similar to two adaptive aiding methodologies discussed by Stokes et al: (a) adaptation to the individual, and (b) adaptation to the situation [7]. Use of these simplifying strategies has made it possible to develop complete systems rapidly and to test their usefulness prior to heavy commitment of resources. Development approaches for these two techniques and the resulting systems will be described, and advantages, disadvantages, and current system status discussed.

OPERATOR TAILORING OF AIDING LEVELS

The prototype NWC Intelligent Air Attack System (IAAS) is designed to aid military tactical pilots in carrying out a few difficult and critical tasks related to an air-to-surface strike mission [8]. The simplifying approach taken for development of this system is *operator tailoring* of the levels of assistance that are provided. This process is related to Wickens's proposed process of *adaptation to the individual* [7].

Adaptive Aiding Approach

Sheridan has proposed 10 possible levels of automation; these 10 levels are equally applicable to the process of operator aiding [9]. All 10 levels *could* be implemented in a system such as IAAS. However, to keep IAAS simple to use and practical for existing Navy, Marine Corps, and Air Force aircraft, only three of these levels of aiding and automation have been incorporated into the prototype system:

1. **INFORM/MONITOR:** the system provides current sensor and other information needed for decision making (via intuitive displays) and alerts the pilot to important events or to deviations from plans; the pilot may ignore the information if he desires (corresponding to Sheridan's Level 2).
2. **RECOMMEND/IMPLEMENT:** the system suggests an action and takes that action upon pilot confirmation; the pilot can override and take a different action if desired (corresponding to Sheridan's Level 5).
3. **AUTOMATE:** the system automatically takes a given action when prespecified conditions are met, and informs the pilot about its actions (corresponding to Sheridan's Level 7).

Using IAAS, the pilot tailors his aiding and automation levels by making various selections during routine premission briefing of the aircraft's computer system. That is, the pilot personally adapts the computer system to suit (a) the specific mission being flown, (b) the tasks required to carry out this mission, and (c) his own "style" of interaction with the aircraft and its systems. He does this by selecting one of the three levels of aiding for each task in a given set. His selections are recorded on a computer cartridge and may be reused indefinitely or may easily be modified if desired (Figure 2).

Advantages of Operator Tailoring

Operator tailoring of the IAAS computer-based adaptive aiding system has a number of advantages, including the following.

1. The system is acceptable to tactical pilots, who do not like autonomous systems and are reluctant to turn over decision-making authority to a computer.
2. The system is relatively simple for the operator to program, since it uses only a few discrete levels of aiding and automation from which only one is selected for each mission task.
3. The user will always know how the system will act and react, since he programmed it himself. Yet the system will not be predictable to an adversary, since various pilots will select different options.
4. The system builds on existing aircraft systems and capabilities rather than replacing them.

Thus IAAS software can be programmed into existing platforms rather than having a special, new aircraft built around it.

- The programs require minimal computer memory and computational assets. As a result, IAAS can be incorporated into existing mission computers rather than requiring the addition of new hardware to aircraft.

Figure 2. Pilot Tailoring of IAAS Aiding and Automation Levels during Pre-mission Briefing of the Aircraft Computers

Disadvantages of Operator Tailoring

For the IAAS programs, the advantages of the operator tailoring technique are partially offset by two disadvantages.

- Operator tailoring requires training for the user to become familiar with the options that are open to him and with the results of various selections.
- Operator tailoring requires considerable time on the operator's part to make all of the required selections. For the IAAS programs, this problem can be overcome somewhat by preparation of several "standard mission" files by the pilot during training. These are retained for personal use; for a given mission, the pilot then simply tailors the selections in one of these files to suit the current strike plan.

Status of IAAS Project

Prototype IAAS software was developed in 1987 and 1988 as a 6.4 (advanced development) project supported by the DoD Joint Service Manpower and Training Technology Development Program. Human performance evaluations and user

satisfaction evaluations will be completed in 1989. Transition of the product to specific aircraft platforms may be possible starting in 1991.

MISSION-PHASE TAILORING OF AIDING LEVELS

The NWC Integrated Energy Management Display (IEMD) project is developing prototype dynamic display formats to aid the fighter pilot during air-to-air battles [10]. These formats are designed to be compatible with the Navy's F/A-18 aircraft and its missions.

The adaptive aiding strategy being used for IEMD development is *mission-phase tailoring* of the levels and kinds of assistance that are provided. This methodology is closely related to the Stokes et al concept of *adaptation to the situation* [7].

Adaptive Aiding Approach

Using the mission-phase tailoring approach, the levels and kinds of aid and information provided to the pilot routinely change with the various phases of the mission. Task automation levels, display media (visual or aural), and display format complexity levels automatically are adapted to the situation as the mission progresses and as pilot tasks and needs change.

Although some researchers are considering as many as 20 mission phases for air combat maneuvering (ACM) situations, for the IEMD prototype system only four phases are being addressed. These phases are (a) intercept, (b) within visual range ACM, (c) weapons delivery, and (d) disengage (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Automatic Mission-Phase Tailoring of IEMD Aiding Levels

Advantages of Mission-Phase Tailoring

Tailoring of the IEMD aiding levels to the mission phase has four advantages.

1. Software for such an aiding system is relatively simple to program, since many applicable computer algorithms already exist.
2. The resulting adaptive aid should be very easy for the pilot to use, if pilots participate in system design, if display media are carefully selected, and if display formats are designed for intuitive understanding.
3. Mission-phase tailoring builds on existing aircraft systems and capabilities, so the software can be added to existing platforms rather than having a special aircraft built around it.
4. Like operator tailoring, mission-phase tailoring requires minimal computer memory and computational assets, so the IEMD formats can be incorporated into existing mission computers rather than requiring addition of new hardware to aircraft.

Disadvantages of Mission-Phase Tailoring

The disadvantages of mission-phase tailoring of the IEMD adaptive aid include the following.

1. Some pilots do not trust and will not use a system that presumes to know what specific kinds of aiding and information they want and need, and when they want such assistance.
2. Expertise of numerous highly-experienced tactical fighter pilots is required for determining the exact aiding and information needed and the exact time it is required. If such experts are not consulted, the resulting system will not be predictable to the pilots who must use it.
3. It is very difficult to design display formats that are intuitively understandable, yet are cognitively compatible with existing aircraft display formats that must be used in the same mission. Since displays are not standardized, generic formats cannot be used; a new set must be designed for each specific fighter aircraft.

Status of IEMD Project

IEMD is a 6.3 (prototype development) project started in 1988. Information required for the four mission phases has been gathered, analyzed, and partitioned among three possible display media: head-up, helmet-mounted, and audio (voice and tone). Prototype display format development will be completed in 1989, and operator evaluations will be started in 1990.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Military pilots generally report that they like the two aiding concepts and the planned IAAS and IEMD implementations. However, such tactical aiding systems are useful and cost-effective only if tests and evaluations demonstrate that the systems significantly enhance mission performance and survivability.

In recent tests, pilots using the IAAS prototype consistently showed performance improvements over pilots carrying out the same mission using a simulated baseline (non-IAAS) aircraft [11]. However, these results still must be considered somewhat inconclusive due to the prototype nature of the system tested. Tests of the prototype IEMD system will be conducted in 1990, and, again, are expected to provide an indication of the usefulness of this aiding concept, but probably not conclusive proof.

A logical next step would be to obtain knowledge about how pilots conduct missions using simple aiding techniques related to operator tailoring and mission-phase tailoring of aids. This knowledge can be incorporated into more accurate models of how the human operator (the pilot) acts in various tactical situations. The resulting models then could be used to program a more comprehensive system that would self-adapt to tactical situations in the same way that an experienced pilot would configure his systems—if he had the time.

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